

**ISOLATED SCALP METASTASIS DEVELOPING 10 YEARS
AFTER DIAGNOSIS OF BREAST CANCER:
A CASE REPORT****Lokman Kiran¹**¹Karaman Eğitim ve Araştırma Hastanesi, Beyin ve Sinir Cerrahisi AD, Karaman, Turkey**ABSTRACT**

Breast cancer is the most common type of cancer in women. Breast cancer is the most common type of cancer that metastasizes to the skin. Isolated scalp metastases are rare in breast cancer. In this study, a breast cancer case with isolated scalp metastasis that developed 10 years after mastectomy is presented.

Keywords: Breast Cancer, Scalp Metastasis

INTRODUCTION

Breast cancer is the most common type of cancer in women (1). Breast cancer is the most common type of cancer that metastasizes to the skin(2). However, scalp involvement is very rare in breast cancer (3). In this study, "a rare case of scalp metastasis that developed after 10 years" of a patient who was diagnosed with breast cancer and underwent mastectomy is presented.

CASE REPORT

An 80-year-old female patient was admitted to the outpatient clinic with complaints of swelling and a palpable mass in the right parietooccipital region (Figure 1-2). Brain CT and contrast-enhanced brain MR examinations were performed on the patient (Figure 3). As a result of the examinations, a mass was detected under the scalp of the patient. Contrast enhancement and dural thickening were evident, especially in the cranium adjacent to the mass. Surgical procedure was planned for our patient. It was observed that the scalp tissue on the mass was severely thinned. The flap was raised around the mass and the mass was excised from the inside towards the scalp. Craniectomy was performed on the contrasting cranium. The thickened dura was incised and duraplasty was performed from the fascia lata. The cranial defect was closed with titanium mesh (Figure 4). In the pathology result of the patient who was discharged on the 4th postoperative day, in the examination of the sections, cells that were not related to the epidermis, partially encapsulated, asymmetrical anastomosis of trabeculae and lobules of different diameters, infiltrative in some areas, occasionally showing ductal differentiation, sebaceous differentiation, and

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mild atypia were observed. Mitosis 1/10 BBA was observed. In the immunohistochemical study, diffuse positivity for CK7 and EMA in the tumor; focal positivity with CEA, GATA-3; sporadic staining with p53; 10% positivity was observed with ki-67. Negativity was observed with p16, CK20, CK5/6. The patient had a diagnosis of breast carcinoma 10 years ago and a history of mastectomy, and the result was determined as malignant breast cancer metastasis.

Figure 1. Breast cancer scalp metastasis

Figure 2. Breast cancer scalp metastasis

Figure 3. Preop MR image

Figure 4. Intraoperatively removed tumor image

DISCUSSION

Breast cancer is the most common malignant tumor worldwide, especially among women. As a matter of fact, approximately 30% of all cancers detected in women are breast cancer (1). In our country, Breast cancer is the most common type of cancer in women. 1 in 4 female cancers is breast cancer. (4). There are 3 treatment methods for breast cancer. These; surgery, radiotherapy and medical treatment(chemotherapy and hormone therapy)(5). Our patient underwent mastectomy 10 years ago and then chemotherapy was applied.

The malignancies that metastasize to the skin in women are, in order of frequency, malignancies of the breast, colon, melanoma, lung, and ovary. Skin metastases are seen in 10% of breast cancer (6). Scalp involvement is very rare in breast cancer (3).

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In patients presenting with a mass in the scalp, biopsy and pathological examinations should be performed from surgical resection materials in terms of cancer risk. Surgical treatment should also be performed in symptomatic cases (severe pain) and lesions that cause aesthetic problems. Extracranial metastases have been reported in the literature as rare case reports for breast cancer. It should be kept in mind that atypically located metastases may be present in breast cancer cases, and it should be kept in mind that curative treatments can be performed in addition to palliative treatments with early diagnosis.

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